

Experimental analysis of solar thermal storage in a water tank with open side inlets

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Abstract

This paper investigates thermal mixing caused by the inflow from one or two round, horizontal, buoyant jets in a water storage tank, which is part of a thermal solar installation. A set of experiments was carried out in a rectangular tank with a capacity of 0.3 m³, with one or two constant temperature inflows. As a result, two correlations based on temperature measurements have been developed. One of the correlations predicts the size of a zone of homogenous temperature, referred to herein as the mixing zone, which develops when a single hot inflow impinges on the opposite wall of the tank. The other identifies the degree of mixing resulting from the interaction between a hot inflow and a cold inflow located below the hot one. The correlations are combined with energy balances to predict the amount of hot water available in a tank with open side inlets and the corresponding temperatures of the outflows. Outdoor measurements were also performed in a solar installation, in which a commercial water storage tank with a 1.5 m³ capacity, heated by a solar collector array with a useful surface area of 42.2 m², drives a LiBr–H₂O absorption chiller. Comparison of the predicted and measured outflow temperatures under a variety of weather conditions shows a maximum difference of 3 °C.

Keywords: Stratified Thermal storage Jets, Solar energy, Load management

1. Introduction

A solar thermal energy storage tank permits excess solar energy to be stored until energy demand exceeds the immediately available solar energy supply. Thermal stratification within the storage tank is preferred because stratification allows the collector to operate at lower temperatures [1], improving solar collector efficiency. Hollands and Lightstone [2] state that the potential improvement in solar energy delivery when a stratified storage tank is used may be as much as 37%, resulting in a significant reduction in auxiliary energy usage [3,4]. In a stratified storage tank, warm water lies directly above cold water with no physical barrier separating them. Consider an inflow with a constant temperature that is higher than the initial water temperature in the tank. In this case, the inflowing water rises to the top of the stratified tank, and a two-layer stratified condition appears. The temperature and density gradients between the two regions in the stratified tank are confined to a relatively thin transition layer called the thermocline. The density gradient across the thermocline dampens mixing between the cold and warm regions.

Conditions that can affect equilibrium in a stratified tank include heat conduction from the warm region of the storage fluid to the cold region, heat conduction along the tank walls, heat losses to the surrounding environment, and mixing caused by buoyant inlet jets during charging and discharging periods. For a properly insulated tank, heat conduction along the walls and heat losses to the surrounding environment are negligible for short storage periods (several days). Consequently, to preserve stratification, hydrodynamic and thermal disturbances caused by the inlet jets must be limited to avoid significant mixing.

The conventional side inlet can be used as a stratifier [5], but a variety of momentum diffuser manifolds with geometries of varying complexity have been proposed to reduce axial inflow momentum and mixing caused by inlet jets [6–10]. Difficulties associated with fitting the more complex manifolds into storage tanks and the cost of the manifolds explain why they have not been more widely adopted. Furthermore, hydrodynamic control alone may be

insufficient to prevent mixing if the temperature difference between the inflow and the region in which the inlet is located is large enough to allow the formation of a strong thermal plume. In order to avoid plume formation due to thermal disequilibrium [11,12], a variety of alternative inlet pipe configurations have been studied [13– 16]. These systems are designed to minimize radial momentum of the incoming buoyant jet, allowing buoyancy forces to drive in- flow to an equilibrium position in the storage tank while limiting mixing of the inflow with water of different temperature.

Minimizing the radial momentum of the incoming jet is difficult, and indirect thermal storage is sometimes preferred. Indirect thermal storage is based on the use of heat exchangers, including jackets (or mantles) on tanks [17-20] and wrap-around coils immersed in the tank [21]. The use of heat exchangers requires higher collector working temperatures, resulting in higher heat losses and/or higher connector costs. Mantle heat exchangers are preferred to wrap-around coils because they typically have larger heat transfer areas, reducing the potential formation of convection plumes. However, the mantle type design is not suitable for tanks with volumes of more than $0.8\text{-}1\text{ m}^3$, and furthermore, mantle heat exchangers require low flow operation in the solar collector loop. Despite performance advantages of indirect thermal storage, direct thermal storage is still commonly used [22-24]. In the designs described in [22-24], physical barriers were used to help limit mixing. However, the thermal and hydrodynamic characteristics of the incoming flow influence the effectiveness of the physical barriers [25] for different degrees of stratification. The present work is aimed at studying the simplest physical barrier - a tank wall opposite an open side inlet jet. Thus, a model of a thermal storage tank of medium size equipped with open side inlets for solar domestic space heating and solar cooling purposes has been experimentally studied.

The goal of the study is to evaluate the temporal evolution of the storage capacity of a water tank with side inlets for a solar installation in the charge and discharge modes. Therefore, the temperature field caused by a buoyant jet that impinges on the tank wall opposite its point of entry in the storage tank has been analysed. The effects of hydrodynamic and thermal characteristics of both singular and dual inlet jets on the temperature field in the tank are reported herein.

2. *Experimental set up*

Outdoor measurements were carried out in the solar plant located in *Planta Experimental de Energía Solar* (CSIC), Arganda del Rey, Madrid, Spain, that Fig.1 shows. The connector array, consisting of 24 vacuum flat-plate solar collectors with a surface area of 42.2 m^2 , supplies thermal energy via an external 25 kW plate heat exchanger to the storage tank. The tank delivers energy to a single effect LiBr-H₂O absorption chiller of the adiabatic absorber type [26].

The storage tank has an inner diameter of .18 m and a height of 1.40 m. The tank is enclosed by a polyurethane foam 80 mm thick. The tank has two pairs of 0.026-m diameter open side ports that connect the tank to the secondary and tertiary loops of the thermal storage system, respectively. Circulation water flows through the secondary loop at a rate of 0.368 kg/s, adding energy from the collector field across the heat exchanger to the tank. Similarly, circulation water flowing at a rate of 0.287 kg/s through the tertiary loop transfers energy to the absorption chiller. The inlet and outlet of the secondary loop are located 0.89 m and 0.34 m above the bottom of the tank, respectively, vertically separated from each other by a distance of 0.55 m. The inlet and outlet of the tertiary loop are 0.44 m and 0.78 m above the bottom of the tank, respectively, and are located between the inlet and outlet of the secondary loop.

Experiments were completed at the University of Nebraska-Lincoln in the experimental apparatus shown in Fig. 2. Tests were done in a 0.609 m by 0.609 m rectangular tank with glass walls and methacrylate base, which represented a thermal storage tank. The depth in the tank was 0.82 m for all of the experiments. The tank is shown with its corresponding hot and cold-water supply, and the temperature measurement system.

A diagram of the rectangular tank is shown in Fig.3. The experimental tank had four ports: two repositionable inlets and two outlets. Each inlet and outlet were equipped with a valve to regulate the flow rate through the port, and the diameters and vertical positions of the inlets were adjustable. The two inlets were connected to two independent constant head supply tanks. The supply tanks, located above the experimental storage tank, allowed independent control of the temperature and flow rate through each of the two inlet ports. The lower and upper outlets were situated at the bottom and top of the tank, respectively. The discharges through the outlets were controlled by a pair of constant head weirs and valves. Flow visualization was carried out by introducing dye into the supply tanks.

Fig. 1 Installation in *Planta Experimental de Energía Solar*, Arganda del Rey (CSIC)

Fig. 2. Experimental setup at the Department of Civil Engineering of the University of Nebraska-Lincoln.

Fig. 3. Diagram of experimental tank (not to scale).

3. Experimental procedure

Prototype measurements were carried out during the summer of 2009 in the *Planta Experimental de Energía Solar* installation. Water temperature was recorded at 1-min intervals using Pt100 thermistors with an uncertainty of ± 0.1 °C. The temperature inside the tank was measured with two sensors, a *top* sensor located 0.11 m above the secondary inlet, and a *bottom* sensor located 0.10 m below the tertiary inlet. The temperatures of the tank in-flows and outflows were also recorded with four sensors, one in each of the inlet and outlet manifolds.

Laboratory measurements were performed during the summer of 2010 at the University of Nebraska-Lincoln. An array of eight type T thermocouples connected to a data acquisition system was used to record various water temperatures at one-second intervals with an uncertainty of ± 0.5 °C. The thermocouples were divided into three groups, each of which was mounted on a different vertical positioning rod, making it easy to position the thermocouples in locations where temperature measurements were required.

The effects of hydrodynamic and thermal properties of the incoming jets on the temperature field in the rectangular tank were studied by collecting the data summarized in Tables 1 and 2. Tests included simulations of three operational modes: charge, simultaneous charge and discharge (combined) and discharge modes. Inlet diameters were adjusted between tests as shown in Tables 1 and 2 for each test. The ranges of measured flow rates, temperatures, and depths below the surface of the upper inlet port are also given in Table 1 for charge mode tests. The mode of operation measured flow rates and depths below the surface of the lower inlet port are summarized in Table 2 for the remaining tests. In these tests, the initial temperature in the tank was between 17.5 and 19.5 °C. and the upper and lower inlet temperatures were fixed values between 43.5 and 45.5 °C and between 17.5 and 19.5 °C, respectively. The depth of the upper inlet nozzle was 0.260 m for Tests 47-52 and 0.155 m for the other tests. The surrounding room temperature was 24 °C for all of the tests.

Table 1. Charge mode tests.

Test	Operation mode	Upper inlet properties					Initial tank Temp. (°C)	Open Outlet
		Inlet diam. ($\times 10^3$ m)	Depth ($\times 10^3$ m)	Temp. (°C)	Discharge (kg/s $\times 10^2$)	l_m/D_T		
1-25	Charge	4.0; 6.7;	9; 19; 32	24-45	1.33-3.24	0.16-1.09	15	Lower
26-36		10.6	16	44-47	2.36-4.20		19	Upper

Table 2. Charge, combined and discharge mode tests.

Test	Operation mode	Upper inlet properties			Lower inlet properties				Open outlet
		Inlet diam. ($\times 10^3$ m)	Discharge (kg/s $\times 10^2$)	l_m/D_T	Inlet diam. ($\times 10^3$ m)	Depth ($\times 10^2$ m)	Discharge (kg/s $\times 10^2$)	l_m/D_T	
37-46	Combined and discharge	5.6; 10.6	3.13-3.62	0.21-0.58	4.0; 5.6; 7.0; 10.6	45	2.50-3.67	0.21-0.67	Both (combined); upper (discharge)
47-52		5.6; 10.6	3.07-3.50	0.20-0.57	7.0; 10.6	37	2.37-3.43	0.20-0.42	
53-65	Combined and discharge	4.0; 5.6; 10.6	2.45-3.52	0.19-0.66	4.0; 5.6; 7.0; 10.6	55	2.57-3.57	0.20-0.87	Both (combined); upper (discharge)
66-88		4.0; 5.6; 7.0; 10.6	2.08-3.80	0.18-0.68	4.0; 5.6; 7.0; 10.6	65	2.50-3.83	0.20-1.06	
89-99		4.0; 5.6; 10.6	3.00-5.80	0.20-0.96	4.0; 5.6; 7.0; 10.6	65	3.22-4.90	0.19-0.90	
100-102	Charge and combined and discharge	7	3.30-3.63	0.38-0.42	4.0; 5.6; 10.6	45	3.37-3.58	0.22-0.90	Upper (charge); both (combined); upper (discharge)
103-105				0.38-0.41		55	3.35-3.50	0.22-0.89	
106-108				0.41-0.41		65	3.37-3.55	0.21-0.89	

4. Experimental results and discussion

4.1. Charge mode

Detailed experimental conditions for Test 1 and Test 20 are given in Table 3. These two tests are representative of the charge mode tests. Fig. 4a and b shows the temporal evolution of the water temperature in the tank for Tests 1 and 20 due to an incoming buoyant jet-like flow of 1.33×10^{-2} kg/s. For these tests, the inlet port was located at a depth of 0.09 m. Prior to each test, the tank was filled with cold water. Then, only the lower outlet port was opened. For Test 1 in Fig. 4a, the diameter of the inlet port was 6.7×10^{-3} m and the temperature of the incoming jet was 30 °C higher than the initial temperature in the tank. For Test 20 in Fig. 4b the inlet port diameter and

temperature difference were 4.0×10^{-3} m and 14°C , respectively.

Table 3 Test conditions for Test 1 and Test 20.

Test	Operation mode	Upper inlet properties					Initial tank Temp. ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Open outlet
		Inlet diam. ($\times 10^3$ m)	Depth ($\times 10^2$ m)	Temp. ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Discharge ($\text{kg/s} \times 10^2$)	l_{in}/D_T		
1	Charge	6.7	9	44	1.33	0.16	15	Lower
20		4	9	28	1.33	0.54		

Fig. 4a shows that the temperature of the water in the tank increases at the same rate for the thermocouples between the free surface and a depth of about 0.11 m for Test 1. The same is true for the thermocouples between the free surface and a depth of about 0.34 m for Test 20 shown in Fig. 3b. Hence, Fig. 4a and b reveals the existence of a homogenous temperature region in the upper part of the tank, referred to herein as the mixing zone. The mixing zone consists of water that warms as it mixes with the hot inlet jet and extends from the top of the tank to a distance z_{m-s} measured from the inlet port downwards.

Fig. 4. Temporal evolution of the water temperature in the tank for Test 1 and Test 20. (a) Test 1: $\Delta T_0 = 30^\circ\text{C}$, inlet diameter = 6.7×10^{-3} m. (b) Test 2: $\Delta T_0 = 14^\circ\text{C}$, inlet diameter = 4.0×10^{-3} m. Thermocouple depths are shown by the arrows.

A horizontal round turbulent buoyant jet, with Reynolds number ranging from 4000 to 20,000 discharges into the tank. The jet impinges on the opposite wall 60–150 jet diameters along the jet axis, far enough from the inlet to assure the flow is fully developed, not being controlled by the inlet port geometry. The jet first travels through the tank and mixes vigorously with the surrounding water by entraining some of the flow. The jet-like flow then impinges on the opposite wall of the tank and spreads in transverse directions, enhancing the mixing process. Part of the flow spreads downward along the wall, but upward buoyancy forces cause the downward spreading component to decelerate to zero velocity. When the inlet jet is within the mixing zone, the downward spreading component may overshoot the lower boundary of the mixing zone, but the flow eventually returns upward to the mixing zone. Baines [27] reported similar behaviour for negatively buoyant two-dimensional plumes adjacent to a wall. Furthermore, the impinging buoyant jet produces a single large recirculation zone located in the upper part of the tank, which also assists the mixing. The lower and upper outlet ports have large diameters of 0.10 and 0.12 m, respectively, resulting in low discharge velocities of only about 4×10^{-2} and 6×10^{-3} m/s, respectively. Therefore, no mixing associated with local turbulence at the outlets is expected.

It was observed that, when water was drawn from the surface (i.e. when the upper outlet port was used), only the temperature of the upper region of the tank increased and the temperature of the water outside of the mixing zone remained constant. However, when the outlet port was located below the mixing zone, Fig. 4a and b shows the temperature of the entire tank volume between the free surface and the outlet eventually increased. Nevertheless, the two deepest thermocouples, initially outside of the mixing zone, show a temporal delay in the temperature rise outside the mixing zone.

Additionally, Fig. 4a and b reveals the existence of a layer, referred to herein as a transition layer, located below the mixing zone, in which the temperature gradient develops. When the lower port is used, as in Tests 1-25, the tank slowly fills with warm buoyant water while the cold water that is initially in the tank is forced out of the lower outlet

port and over the control weir. Accordingly, the size of the transition layer increases downward as a consequence of the warmed water leaving the mixing zone. If thermal diffusion is neglected, it is expected that the size of the transition layer increases at a rate equivalent to the ratio of the volumetric flow rate of the inflow and the cross-sectional area of the tank; this ratio is defined as the interface velocity. When the outlet port is located within the mixing zone, as it was in the set of experiments that includes Tests 26-36, the interface velocity is zero. Hence, for these tests the transition layer thickness is at a minimum and remains nearly constant during the heating process. In this case, the transition layer may consist of two different sub-layers. The upper sub-layer was observed to have the weaker temperature gradient due to the axisymmetric configuration of the jet-like flow that, in addition to the overshoot phenomenon, results in weak mixing. The lower sub-layer, a non-convective sub-layer, is apparently dominated by heat conduction [28].

For a round buoyant jet, two relevant length scales are I_Q and I_M , defined as

$$I_Q = \frac{Q}{M^{1/2}} \quad \text{and} \quad I_M = \frac{M^2}{R^1} \quad (1)$$

where Q , M and B are the initial values of volume flux, specific momentum flux and specific buoyancy flux, respectively [11,12]. In confined flow, the tank diameter measured along the axis of the jet, D_T , is also a relevant length scale. Since I_Q is primarily associated with the length of flow establishment, it is not as important as the remaining two variables, I_M and D_T , for a stabilized flow. Consequently, we express a dimensionless form of the mixing zone thickness below the inlet port, z_{m-s} , with the relation:

$$z_{m-s}/D_T = f(I_M/D_T) \quad (2)$$

The dimensionless parameter I_M/D_T represents the value of I_M/z reached by the incoming buoyant jet when it impinges on the tank wall, z being the distance along the jet axis. It states the importance of buoyancy versus momentum when the inflow reaches the wall. On the other hand, Z_{m-s}/D_T is the ratio of the terminal height of rise of the negatively buoyant flow resulting after the inflow impact to the characteristic length of the tank.

To make sure the buoyant jet impinges directly onto the wall, its trajectory should be roughly horizontal, that is, the buoyant jet acts like a jet. Accordingly, the minimum value of the ratio momentum length I_M to the distance of the wall along the jet axis D_T was about 0.18 in the experiments, what guarantees the buoyant jet has not turned into a plume before reaching the wall. In the experiments carried out, I_M/D_T ranged from 0.18 to 1.1, that is, always near 1 or lower. This means that the buoyant inflow was always more like a plume than a jet when reached the wall. The maximum value of I_M/D_T was limited to 1.1 to avoid the inflow reached the base of the tank after hitting the wall.

Fig. 5 shows two sets of experimental values of Z_{m-s}/D_T , obtained with the outlet port located inside of and outside of the mixing zone. The increased scatter associated with having the outlet port outside of the mixing zone is a consequence of the difficulty of identifying its boundary when the temperature gradient in the transition layer is weak, as a consequence of the warmed water leaving the mixing zone.

Fig. 5. Dimensionless mixing zone thickness, Z_{m-s}/D_T , as a function of the dimensionless characteristic length I_M/D_T . Data represent experiments for two different outlet positions (Tests 1-36).

When the outlet is located outside of the mixing zone, the interface velocity is superimposed onto the velocity field

in the tank. However, the difference between the two data sets is negligible, and it can be concluded that the effect of superimposing a vertical flow on the size of the mixing zone is negligible, at least when the interface velocity does not exceed 8.33×10^{-4} m/s, the highest interface velocity in the present data set.

Fitting a line to the data in Fig. 5 results in the equation:

$$z_{m-s}/D_T = 0.9085 l_M/D_T - 0.1965 \quad (3)$$

which has a high correlation coefficient of 0.99.

Experiments performed with the outlet port located at the top of the tank reveal that the thickness of the transition layer ranges from about 0.06 m when l_M/D_T is 0.18, to beyond 0.16 m when l_M/D_T is 1.1. The tendency of the transition layer thickness to increase with l_M may be caused by the overshoot phenomena, which strengthens as l_M increases. Furthermore, the water tank warms up more slowly as the thickness of the transition layer increases. Consider the storage tank when it is operating in charge mode with only the upper outlet port open. Under the assumptions that the inflow mixes mainly with the water in the mixing zone and that heat losses to the surroundings are negligible, the thickness of a theoretical homogeneous warm region, z_{m-} , measured underneath the inlet port, may be determined from the energy rate balance applied to the mixing zone, which takes the form

$$\rho \cdot (H_{inlet} + z_{m-}) \cdot D_T^2 \cdot \frac{dT}{dt} = \dot{m}_H \cdot (T_H - T) \quad (4)$$

where H_{inlet} is the depth at which the inlet is located, and \dot{m}_H and T_H are the mass flow rate and the temperature of the inflow, respectively. Heat losses to surroundings are negligible when

$$\frac{qA}{c\dot{m}_H} \ll T_H$$

where q is the heat loss per surface area, A is the wall surface area and c is the specific heat capacity of water. Considering the tank was located indoors, its overall heat transfer coefficient was about $9.12 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Additionally, room temperature was kept constant during the tests, at about $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Hence, assuming a maximum temperature gradient to surroundings of about $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the maximum heat rate exchanged per surface area, qA , was about 132.5 W . Therefore, the previous condition is equivalent to

$$T_H \gg 0.76^\circ\text{C}$$

a requirement that was met for every test carried out in charge mode.

Fig. 6 shows that z_{m-} is always greater than z_{m-s} , especially at high values of l_M/D_T , as a consequence of the thermal energy stored in the transition layer. A fit of the thickness of the theoretical homogeneous warm region yields

$$z_{m-}/D_T = 0.903(l_M/D_T)^{1.3467} \quad (5)$$

In the next section it will be shown that this regression accurately estimates the size of the region that includes the mixing zone plus the transition layer.

Fig. 6. Theoretical dimensionless thickness of the mixing zone, z_{m-s}/D_T , as a function of the dimensionless characteristic length l_M/D_T . Corresponding values of z_{m-}/D_T are also shown.

Accordingly, the effect of the height/diameter aspect ratio of the thermal storage tank, AR , the inlet diameter, d , or the height of the hot inflow inlet from the top of the tank, H_H , on the level of thermal stratification in the tank can be handled in a unified way.

Thus, consider the total volume of the mixing zone, V , calculated as adding the volume of the one with height H_H , V_1 , to that with height z_m , V_2 . It seems reasonable to consider that the initial value of V , V_0 , will play a main role in level of thermal stratification for a preset rate of energy supply since it will determine the transient temperature response of the mixing zone.

At low values of l_M/D_T and H_H , that is, at low V_0 , the mixing zone temperature quickly approaches the inflow temperature. As a consequence, the mixing zone enlarges quickly. When V_0 is low enough, the mixing zone widening rate and the interface velocity will reach similar values, and the transition layer will remain thin, indicating good thermal stratification. Conversely, at high values of l_M/D_T , that is, at high V_0 , the temperature at the mixing zone will hardly ever increase. The result is a broad transition layer as a consequence of the warmed water that is pushed out of the mixing zone by the hot inflow. Consequently, the level of thermal stratification will drop off.

Such behaviour was observed in Tests 1 and 20, both with the same inlet position, that is, with equal values for V_l . Nevertheless, for Test 1 the initial value of l_M/D_T was 0.16, and so V_0 was 0.041 m². For Test 20, the initial values of l_M/D_T and V_0 were, however, 0.58 and 0.126 m², respectively. Thus, transient temperature rises faster in Test 1. Additionally, the transition layer broadened notably during Test 20. Thus, after 1820 s, the temperature through the transition layer fell 6 °C in a thickness of 0.04 m and l_M/D_T reached 0.22 for Test 1. Conversely, for Test 20, the temperature barely dropped as much as 1 °C in 0.12 m through the transition layer, and l_M/D_T did not exceed 0.62.

Consider an energy storage tank of preset capacity V_T and mass flow rate m_H . Note that, since $D_T \propto (V_T/AR)^{1/3}$, V_0 decreases slowly as AR is increased. On the other hand, $l_M/D_T \propto (m_H/d^{3/2})$, thus, V_0 increases notably as d is decreased. Additionally, $V_0 \propto H_H$. Consequently, a high level of thermal stratification is expected when the aspect ratio is high, the inlet diameter is large, and the inlet of the hot inflow is positioned near the top of the tank. Nevertheless, the destratifying effect of the overshoot phenomenon, which strengthens as l_M/D_T increases as Fig. 6 shows, must also be considered. Hence, low l_M/D_T inflows are preferred.

Numerical simulation results reported by [29] show similar behaviour.

4.2. Charge-discharge mode

Under ordinary conditions, thermal storage tanks usually operate in charge mode less than 2 h - at the beginning of a sunny day, for example. The thermal load is then applied once the water temperature in the tank reaches a predetermined threshold, and the tank begins to operate in combined mode. The return flow from the thermal load has a lower temperature than the warmed layer and enters the tank through a second inflow port, usually located near the bottom of the tank. Therefore, the resulting temperature distribution caused by the interaction of two parallel horizontal jets at different depths and with different temperatures was also studied.

Detailed test conditions are given for two charge-discharge mode tests, Tests 103 and 105, in Table 4. Fig. 7a and b shows the water temperature at several positions for Tests 103 and 105. Hot and cold inlets were fixed 0.36 m apart. The two tests have similar inlet diameter, temperature and mass flow rate of the hot discharge: 7×10^{-3} m, 44.5 °C and 3.3×10^{-2} kg/s, respectively. As a result, the value of l_M/D_T is nearly the same for both tests, namely 0.38 for Test 103 and 0.41 for Test 105. Accordingly, it is expected that the equilibrium size of the warm mixing zone will also be similar. The temperature of cold inflows was 17.9°C for both tests. However, the temperature evolution in the tank was noticeably different.

Table 4. Test conditions for Test 103 and Test 105.

Test	Operation mode	Upper inlet properties			Lower inlet properties			Open outlet	
		Inlet diam. ($\times 10^3$ m)	Discharge (kg/s $\times 10^2$)	l_M/D_T	Inlet diam. ($\times 10^3$ m)	Depth ($\times 10^2$ m)	Discharge (kg/s $\times 10^2$)		l_M/D_T
103	Charge and combined and discharge	7	3.3	0.38	10.6	55	3.5	0.22	Upper; both; upper
105			3.57	0.41	4		3.35		

Fig. 7. Temperature evolution for (a) Test 103 and (b) Test 105. Inlet diameter of the cold inflow: (a) 10.6×10^{-3} m; (b) 4.0×10^{-3} m. Thermocouple depths are shown by the arrows.

In Test 103, the tank was initially charged by the hot inflow. While the tank was charging, the upper outlet port was open and the lower outlet port was closed. The tank was operating in the charge mode for a 1620 s period, after which a cold inlet jet, located 0.36 m below the hot inlet, was turned on and a combined mode test was initiated. At the same time, the lower outlet port was opened so that the outflow through the upper outlet port remained constant and the inflow from the new jet exited entirely through the lower outlet. The temperature of the cold inlet jet was the same as that of the undisturbed water in the bottom of the tank. Thus, the lower jet was not expected to display any buoyancy characteristics. The warm inlet jet was stopped 820 s after the combined mode test began, resulting in the subsequent discharge of the tank. The same procedure was followed in Test 105. In this case the charge and the subsequent charge/discharge mode sequences were 1450 and 1016 s long, respectively.

Fig. 7a shows that the cold inflow barely disturbed the temperature field when the combined mode test began, and only the very lowest part of the transition layer was affected. Note that the thermocouples located at 0.35 and 0.33 m below the free surface are the only ones that showed a drop in temperature following start-up of the lower jet. However, the response observed in Test 105 was quite different. Fig. 7b shows that when the second jet was turned on at 1450 s, most of the temperatures measured where the transition layer was located immediately began to decline. In addition, the water near the bottom of the tank that had remained undisturbed throughout the charging process began to warm up when the cold jet was started. The cold jet also caused the transition layer to become thicker. Consequently, the thermocouples initially located at depths of 0.28, 0.30 and 0.32 m, were raised 0.12 m to track the new size of the mixing zone, which differed from that attributed to the mixing zone for the solitary inflow, z_{m-s} . At the same time, the thermocouples located at depths of 0.31, 0.33 and 0.35 m were lowered 0.17 m to measure the downward growth of the transition layer.

Fig. 7b reveals that the cold inflow caused strong mixing during Test 105. It should be noted that the inflow momentum of the cold jet during Test 103 was $1.39 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^4/\text{s}^2$ versus $8.94 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^4/\text{s}^2$ in Test 105. The increase in inflow momentum appears to be the cause of the mixing. For both tests, the cold inflow entered the tank at a point outside of the warm mixing zone. Although the temperatures of the cold inflow and the lower region of the tank were the same, buoyancy forces were important in the interaction of the cold inflow and the warmed layer. Since a cold mixing zone was observed at the bottom of the tank, a new parameter, l_M/D_T , was defined for the cold inflow as

$$\frac{l_M}{D_T} \equiv \frac{M^{3/4}}{B^{1/2} \cdot D_T} \quad (6)$$

where the specific buoyant flow B at the inlet is based on the temperatures of the cold inflow T_C and the warm mixing zone T_1 . In Tests 103 and 105, values of l_M/D_T for the cold inlet jet were 0.22 and 0.89, respectively. Thus, the temperature field in the tank gets more disturbed as l_M/D_T increases.

One way to quantify the disturbance caused by the cold inflow is to evaluate the rate at which the temperature of the charged layer increases. This parameter, in addition to the size of the homogenous warm region, determines the storage capacity of the tank in the combined mode. Assume that the storage tank is operating in the combined mode, with the upper and lower outlet ports open. Under these conditions, the upper warm region can exchange

water with the lower cold region in two ways. First, a net downward flow rate may result if the hot inflow exceeds the volume flow rate capacity of the upper outlet port. Second, interaction between the warm and the cold regions can induce mixing. Assuming that the two inflows develop inside the tank without interfering with each other, that is, that their recirculation zones behave independently, the energy rate balances applied to both the warm and the cold mixing zones take the form

$$\rho \cdot (H_{hotinlet} + z_2) \cdot D_T^2 \cdot \frac{dT_1}{dt} = \dot{m}_H \cdot (T_H - T_1) + (\dot{m}_C - \dot{m}_l) \cdot (T_2 - T_1) + \dot{m}_{sh} \cdot (T_2 - T_1) \quad (7)$$

and

$$\rho \cdot (H_T - H_{coldinlet} + |z_1|) \cdot D_T^2 \cdot \frac{dT_2}{dt} = \dot{m}_C \cdot (T_C - T_2) + \dot{m}_{sh} \cdot (T_1 - T_2) \quad (8)$$

where m_{sh} refers to the rate at which the warm and cold mixing zones, at temperatures T_1 and T_2 , respectively, exchange mass flow with each other at time t . The mass flows that enter and exit through the lower inlet and outlet ports are referred to as m_C and m_l , respectively. Additionally, z_1 and z_2 refer, respectively, to the sizes of the mixing zones of each inflow when operating independently, evaluated with Eq. (5).

A mixing parameter, α , defined as $\alpha \equiv m_{sh}/m_H$, may be approximately determined with Eq. (7) when the other variables in the equation are experimentally measured. Similarly, α can also be determined using Eq. (8). This parameter quantifies the mass flow exchange between the warm and cold regions as a fraction of the hot inflow mass rate. Since the value of α must be the same independent of which equation is used, the equations can be used to determine the conditions for which the non-interfering assumption is appropriate.

Heat losses can be neglected in Eqs. (7) and (8) provided that

$$\frac{q_H A_H}{c \dot{m}_H} \ll T_H, \quad \frac{q_H A_H}{c \dot{m}_H} \ll \alpha(T_2 - T_1)$$

and

$$\frac{q_C A_C}{c \dot{m}_C} \ll T_C, \quad \frac{q_C A_C}{c \dot{m}_C} \ll \alpha(T_2 - T_1)$$

where q_H and q_C , are the heat loss per surface area in the warm and cold regions, respectively. A_H and A_C refer to their surface areas. The previous conditions are equivalent to

$$T_C, T_H \gg 0.4^\circ\text{C} \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha \gg 0.04$$

Both conditions were fulfilled in all the experiments performed. The variable α is expected to be dependent on l_M/D_T , through z_m , for each inflow, and on the distance ΔH between the two inlets. Thus, the mixing parameter α may depend on the overlap extent between the mixing zones of the warm and cold inflows, z_2 and z_1 , respectively. Hence, the dimensionless overlap extent parameter, $\Delta z_m/D_T$, is defined as follows:

$$\frac{\Delta z_m}{D_T} \equiv \frac{z_1 + z_2 - \Delta H}{D_T} \quad (9)$$

This parameter quantifies the overlap between the warm and cold regions based on the characteristic tank length. Note that the overlap parameter is implicitly based on ΔH and on the l_M/D_T value for each inflow.

Fig. 8 shows the evolution of α with $\Delta z_m/D_T$ for non-interfering inflows. The figure shows that α increases nearly linearly when the mixing zones overlap. It is observed that the following regression fits the experimental data very well.

$$\alpha = \begin{cases} 0.3 & \frac{\Delta z_m}{D_T} < -0.03 \\ 4.9741 \frac{\Delta z_m}{D_T} + 0.4739 & -0.03 \leq \frac{\Delta z_m}{D_T} \leq 0.44 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

The l_M/D_T domain that extents from 0.18 to 0.9 for the hot and cold inflows was tracked minutely by experiments. They revealed that a low value of l_M/D_T does not guarantee the validity of the non-interfering assumption. This is a consequence of the important role that ΔH plays through $\Delta z_m/D_T$. However, experimental results show that a low value of $\Delta z_m/D_T$ does not guarantee the validity of the non-interfering assumption either. This hypothesis assumes that the mixing zone of an inflow is not altered by the existence of a second inflow. Hence, the distance of the edge of the mixing zone induced by the first inflow should be sufficiently far from the inlet port of the second inflow to prevent interference. Fig. 9 shows that, in addition to inflows that do not overlap (measurements above line A), inflows that overlap can be considered non-interfering provided that they fulfil the following condition (measurements above line B).

$$\Delta H - z_1 > 0.5z_2 \quad (\text{or } \Delta H - z_2 > 0.5z_1) \quad (11)$$

Fig. 8. The mixing parameter, α , plotted versus $\Delta z_m/D_T$

Nevertheless, this condition may be relaxed when l_M/D_T is similar for both inflows, as three of the measurements enclosed by curve D show. The measurements where $\Delta H - z_1 < 0$ (or $\Delta H - z_2 < 0$), shown under line C, are always considered to be interfering inflows.

According to the non-interference hypothesis, the positions of the superior and inferior boundaries of the transition layer in non-interfering inflows should be in agreement with those of a solitary inflow, z_2 and z_1 . Fig. 10 shows the location of the transition layer when the mixing zones do not overlap. Measured values for the superior boundary agree well with those predicted with Eq. (5). The same is true for the observed inferior boundaries and their predicted values using Eq. (3).

Fig. 9. Experimental measurements in the combined mode. $(\Delta H - z_1)/D_T$ versus z_2/D_T

When the mixing zones overlap, the location of the lower boundary of the transition layer may be estimated by the value z_2 obtained by entering l_M/D_T for the cold inflow in Eq. (5), establishing how far the cold inflow is able to penetrate into the warm mixing zone. Similarly, the upper boundary of the transition layer may be estimated as z_1

obtained by entering l_M/D_T for the hot inflow in Eq. (5). Agreement between the measurements and estimations is reasonable. Nevertheless, Fig. 11 shows that the upper boundary location is underestimated by 10% when l_M/D_T of the cold inflow is lower than 0.6. Furthermore, this figure shows that the error increases as either l_M/D_T of the cold inflow decreases, or l_M/D_T of the hot inflow increases. This behaviour can be attributed to the lower momentum of the cold inflow, which allows the warm mixing zone to pull the cold one upwards, enlarging the transition layer. This effect seems to have no influence on the mixing parameter value.

Additionally, it was found that, for flows in which the mixing zones do not overlap, the thicknesses are the same as those of solitary inflows. When the mixing zones overlap, the figure reveals that the thickness of the transition layer increases at the same rate as the overlap parameter.

In order to prevent mixing in the tank during charge–discharge mode, ΔH should be preset large enough to avoid initial overlapping between the mixing zones. Nevertheless, l_M/D_T of one or both inflows could increase during the tank operation when the temperature inflow approaches to the temperature of the mixing zone on which discharges. Eventually, mixing zones could overlap. In this scenario, minimizing the degree of mixing requires the lowest l_M/D_T for both inflows. This is because, according to Eq. (5), the enlargement of a mixing zone caused by a certain decrease of buoyancy flux is proportional to momentum flux, and so, to l_M/D_T .

Fig. 10. Transition layer for non-interfering inflows. Position of the transition layer when the inflows do not overlap versus l_M/D_T for the warm inflow.

Fig. 11. Error in the estimation of z_1 for non-interfering inflows.

4.3. Discharge mode

In typical applications, the heat source is disconnected when the temperature of the water coming from the solar collector array drops below a preset threshold. If the thermal load remains connected, the storage tank enters the discharge mode, in which only the inferior cold inlet jet is still discharging flow.

Table 5 provides details of Tests 68 and 94, two discharge mode tests. Fig. 12a and b shows the temperature evolution in the tank for Tests 68 and 94, first during the charge-discharge mode with- out and with mixing (ex is equal to 03 and 2.6, respectively), and then during the subsequent discharge mode. In both tests, the inlet jets are separated from each other by 0.46 m. Table 5 shows that l_M/D_T for the cold jet inflow reached a similar value in both tests, about 0.55. Additionally, the cold discharge was similar for both tests, causing a bulk average emptying velocity of approx. 9.17×10^{-4} m/s.

Table 5. Test conditions for Test 68 and Test 74.

Test	Operation mode	Upper inlet properties			Lower inlet properties				Open outlet
		Inlet diam. ($\times 10^3$ m)	Discharge (kg/s $\times 10^2$)	l_M/D_T	Inlet diam. ($\times 10^3$ m)	Depth ($\times 10^2$ m)	Discharge (kg/s $\times 10^2$)	l_M/D_T	
68	Combined and discharge	10.6	3.33	0.21	5.6	65	3.33	0.55	Both; upper
74		4	3.1	0.81	5.6		3.55	0.56	

Fig. 12. Temperature evolution during the charge-discharge mode and the subsequent discharge mode for (a) Test 68 and (b) Test 94. l_M/D_T for the warm inflows: (a) 0.21, (b) 0.81. Thermocouple depths are shown by the arrows.

The tank is initially charged for the two non-interfering inflows. When the discharge mode begins (after a 2400 s period for Test 68 and a 10,700 s period for Test 94), the cold inflow pushes the transition layer, and the warm region that rests above it, towards the upper outlet port. The displacement rate of the transition layer was calculated by recording the time it took the layer to travel between two predetermined depths (A and B in the figures). Note that the temperature gradient in the transition layer remains for the duration of the discharge process (1020 s long for Test 68 and 2520 s long for Test 94), independent of the degree of mixing in the tank. Consequently, the transition layer moves at constant velocity. Nevertheless, for long discharge processes, it was observed that the temperature gradient does decrease when the transition layer was formed by non-mixing inflows. This behaviour is attributable to the erosion of the non-convective sub-layer that is typical of transition layers formed by non-mixing inflows; this erosion occurs during the discharge process. Fig. 7a demonstrates this behaviour overall discharge period of about 2340 s (note the difference in the temperature gradient observed 0.07 and 0.28 m from the surface).

Fig. 13 shows the predicted expansion velocity of the cold water zone due to the cold inflow versus the measured displacement rate of the transition layer. The tank was initially charged when operating in the combined mode with non-interfering inflows. Data scatter is at least in part due to the difficulty in determining the elapsed time between A and B.

Fig. 13 reveals that the position of the transition layer does not change abruptly once the hot inflow is suppressed at the beginning of the discharge mode. This fact shows that the cold inflow does not influence the hydrodynamic characteristics of the mixing zone associated with the hot inlet jet, corroborating the assumption about the superposition of non-interfering inflows.

Fig. 13. Displacement rate of the lower boundary of the mixing zone plotted versus the cold water zone expansion velocity associated with the cold inflow.

4.3. Comparison between predicted and experimental results in a water tank operating in a solar installation

The temperature evolution of the water storage tank was simulated and compared with the measurements in the solar installation *Planta Experimental de Energía Solar* (CSIC).

This round tank was tested in similar conditions to the rectangular tank, with regard to convective entrainment, heat losses to surroundings and heat diffusion to the cold mixing region due to temperature gradient. Thus, heat losses to surroundings were governed by its overall heat transfer coefficient per surface area, $0.548 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Assuming surroundings and tank water temperatures of about 35 and 85 $^\circ\text{C}$, respectively, heat losses were about 41.1 W. This means 0.28%, 0.36% and 1.42% of the net thermal power exchanged by the tank through the inflows in the charge, charge-discharge and discharge modes, respectively. Tank operation characterized by $1_M/D_T$ for the hot and cold inflows of about 0.5 and 0.4, respectively, conditions tested with the rectangular tank. Finally, gradient temperature between the warm and cold regions was of about 10 $^\circ\text{C}$, similar to that in the rectangular tank.

Conversely, in the round tank a net flow towards the base of the tank had to be considered. Nevertheless, the corresponding inter-face velocity, of about $7.9 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m/s}$, is considered not high enough to modify the size of the mixing zones. Additionally, inflow temperatures did not remain constant during the experiments.

A numerical simulation was implemented by assuming the tank has a two-layer configuration at all times.

Consequently, the existence of two regions with homogeneous temperature separated from each other by a transition layer where a temperature gradient develops is assumed.

Based on the aforementioned experimental results, the size of the warm (cold) region plus the transition layer may be estimated with Eq. (5) in the charge (discharge) mode. Nevertheless, it should be noted that the inflow temperatures are not held constant in these simulations. Consequently, the size of the mixing zones may increase or decrease as the inflow temperature changes, according to Eq (5). However, the numerical approach proposed herein only models expansion of the size of the region affected by the inflow. This is a realistic assumption when $1_M/D_T$ is not high enough so that the inflow penetrates the outer region. However, the approach allows an inflow with a new temperature to influence the same region that it did prior to the temperature change even if the size of the new mixing zone is predicted to be smaller.

In the combined mode, the size of the warm or cold regions plus the transition layer is predicted with Eq. (5) when the inflows overlap. In this case, the degree of mixing is evaluated with Eq. (10).

Nevertheless, when the inflows do not overlap, each inflow spreads, filling the region that extends beyond its inlet up to the boundary determined by the second inflow. Consequently, the size of the warm and/or cold regions remains constant until one of the inflows penetrates the region established by the second inflow.

Accordingly, the numerical approach may be summarized as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{recirculating zones do not overlap : } \left\{ \begin{array}{l} z_i : \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{evaluated with Eq.5 until its maximum value is reached, } z_{i\max} \\ z_{i\max}, \text{ otherwise} \end{array} \right. \\ z_j = \Delta H - z_i \end{array} \right. \\ \text{recirculating zones overlap : } \left\{ \begin{array}{l} z_i : \text{evaluated with Eq.5} \\ z_j : \text{evaluated with Eq.5} \end{array} \right. \end{array} \right.$$

$$\alpha : \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{evaluated with Eq.10, if } z_i < \Delta H, z_j < \Delta H \text{ and } \Delta z_m/D_T \leq 4.4 \\ \text{the tank is fully mixed or unstratified, otherwise} \end{array} \right.$$

In the experiments performed in the rectangular tank, the incoming flow impinged directly on the wall opposite its inlet. As a result, flow spread transversely enhancing mixing. Simulation assumes that the inflow mixes completely in the mixing region. Thus, cross-section shape plays a secondary role, being only its surface area significant. Consequently, round tanks are considered suitable to test the proposed simulation.

Fig. 14a and b shows experimental results for the tests carried out on June 15 and June 4, 2009, respectively. During both tests, the tank operated in the charge, combined and discharge modes. The figures show the evolution of the measured and predicted temperatures of the upper and lower outflows, T_1 and T_2 , towards the absorption chiller (tertiary loop) and the heat exchanger (secondary loop), respectively. The figures also show the measured temperatures of the upper and lower inflows, T_H and T_C , respectively. Additionally, the temperatures registered by the *Top* and *Bottom* sensors are shown. Fig. 15a and b shows the mixing parameter and the fraction of hot water storage predicted in each test.

Fig. 14a shows the predicted and measured temperatures in the tank during a test carried out on 15 June 2009. On this day, a sunny morning was followed by a cloudy afternoon. The tank was operating in the charge mode with the chiller disconnected from 8:10 until 10:00, when T_1 reached 77 °C. Fig. 15a shows that the hot water storage capacity was about 74% when the charge mode ended. At 10:00 the absorption chiller was connected but it did not start up until 10:30, once T_1 reached 78 °C. Because of the small temperature difference between T_C and T_1 , the cold region enlarged quickly, until it exceeded the upper inlet port, at 10:05. At this time, it was assumed that the tank was fully mixed, reaching 100% of its storage capacity. Once the tank had reached 78 °C, at 10:30, the chiller started. This caused the temperature difference between T_C and T_1 to decrease. As a result, a small cold region associated with the lower inflow developed. Tank stratification was recovered, decreasing the hot water storage capacity to 54% as Fig. 15a shows. Then, T_1 gradually increased due to solar gain until 13:08, when T_H dropped as the sky became cloudy. Fig. 15a shows that the fraction of the hot water stored did not change at this time. This means that the upper inflow was not able to penetrate the cold region. To avoid the subsequent fall of T_1 , the upper inflow was interrupted at that moment, causing the tank to operate in discharge mode. From that moment, the upper inflow was interrupted several times. As a result, the tank was successively charged and discharged. Nevertheless, the temperature of the upper outflow remained higher than 88 °C. as Fig. 15a shows. At 15:40, the upper boundary of the transition layer reached the level of the upper outlet, causing the temperature of the upper outflow to fall dramatically, and stopping the chiller.

Fig. 14. Measured and predicted temperatures in the storage tank of a solar thermal installation. (a) Results on 15 June 2009.(b) Results on 4 June 2009.

Fig. 15a shows that charging of the tank occurred mostly without mixing, as shown by α , which did not exceed 0.3. However, the temperature in the cold region was at all times higher than T_C - a consequence of the water coming from the warm region at a rate of the difference between the secondary and tertiary loop flow rates. However, after 15:00, mixing zones overlapped at the end of each charging process due to the low T_H values, enhancing mixing. The maximum difference between predicted and measured outflow temperatures was 3 °C. Hence, the model gave reliable results for every process in the tank.

Fig. 14b and 15b show estimated and experimental results in a test carried out on 4 June 2009, a cloudy day with low solar gain. The charge mode began at 9:47. The storage tank showed an increase in the fraction of hot water storage until it reached 65%. However, the temperature of the hot water clearly decreased due to the low value of T_H . At 9:47 the chiller began working. The fraction of storage water fell continuously as the cold region enlarged due to the T_C increase. The upper inflow was disrupted numerous times due to its low temperature. The low value of T_H caused an increase in the hot water fraction in the tank and additional mixing, due to overlap of the mixing zones. In fact, Fig 15b reveals that α increased up to 0.8 prior to each interruption. Nevertheless, subsequent charge and discharge processes provided a continuous energy supply to the chiller until 12:43. At this time, the transition layer reached the level of the upper outlet. The discharge process was then stopped because of the low temperature of the water delivered by the tank. The maximum difference between the predicted and measured outflow temperatures was 3 °C. The discrepancies between the predicted and measured outflow temperatures are reasonable.

Fig. 15. Mixing parameter and fraction of hot water storage: (a) Results on 15 June 2009.(b) Results on 4 June 2009.

5. Conclusions

Thermal stratification in a storage water tank with open side in- lets for a solar installation has been modelled. Three modes of operation have been studied, namely, the charge, charge–discharge and discharge modes.

The model assumes the existence of two non interfering regions of homogeneous temperature and a transition layer as a result of their overlap. The condition that assures the validity of this hypothesis was established. The size of every region has been identified from experiments, along with the relevant inflow characteristics and temperature environment. The mass and energy transferred between regions is modelled by an experimentally estimated mixing coefficient, α .

Results show that, for a certain energy storage tank with fixed capacity and mass flow rate, the values chosen for the set of parameters including tank diameter, inlet diameter and inlet position from the top, which achieves high level of stratification in charge and discharge mode, should be those that involve a low initial volume for the mixing zone. Additionally, distance between in- let ports should be high enough to avoid mixing zones overlapping when the tank operates on charge–discharge mode. Nevertheless, low l_M/D_T inflows are always preferred. Even so, the best arrangement will depend on the specific inflow temperature profile.

A commercial water tank with open side inlets and 1.5 m³ of capacity, heated by a solar collector array with a useful surface area of 42.2 m² was modelled. Simulations were performed considering diverse inflow temperature profiles, related to very different thermal loads. Comparison of the predicted and measured outflow temperatures shows that the outflow temperatures were estimated with an uncertainty of less than 3°.

The proposed model does not take into account additional mixing due to factors such as thermal diffusion or the effects of the repetitive charge and discharge of the tank. However, the results of the model suggest that these factors play a secondary role in the prediction of the fraction of hot water storage for short storage periods. The advantage of the proposed modelling method is that it is simpler and less time-consuming than CFD modelling.

Nomenclature

AR	aspect ratio
B	specific buoyancy flux (m ⁴ s ⁻³)
D _T	tank diameter (m)
H _{inlet}	depth at which the inlet is located (m)
D _H	distance between the two inlets (m)
l _M	characteristic length (m)
l _Q	characteristic length (m)
M	specific momentum flux (m ⁴ s ⁻²)
m _C	mass flow rate of the cold inflow (kg/s)
m _H	mass flow rate of the hot inflow (kg/s)
m _I	mass flow rate that exits through the lower outlet port (kg/s)
m _{xh}	mass flow rate that the warm and cold mixing zones exchange (kg/s)
Q	volume flux (m ³ s ⁻¹)
T _H	temperature of the hot inflow (°C)
T _C	temperature of the cold inflow (°C)
Z _{m-s}	thickness of a theoretical homogeneous warm region(m)
Z _{m-}	mixing zone thickness below the inlet port (m)
Δ _{zm}	overlap parameter (m)

Greek letters

α	mixing parameter
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Subscripts

C	cold
H	hot
1	superior
2	inferior

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